

PERCEPTION OF FARMERS TOWARDS CROP RAIDING BY WILD ANIMALS IN PATUR TAHSIL OF AKOLA DISTRICT, MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

The study entitled "Perception of farmers towards crop raiding by wild animals in Patur Tahsil of Akola District, Maharashtra" during 2024–25. A total of 120 respondents from four villages were selected through simple random sampling, and data were collected using structured interviews. Most respondents were in the old age group (49.17%), had completed secondary education (30.00%), and reported having a well on their farm (62.50%). The majority were small (45.83%) and semi-medium (24.17%) landholders with low annual incomes (85.84%) and farms located close to forest areas (81.67%) within 0–0.5 km. Wild boar (100%) and blue bull (96.67%) emerged as the predominant species causing damage, with deer (27.50%) and monkeys (24.17%) also contributing. The majority of farmers (67.00%) reported severe crop damage and (92.00%) observed yield reductions, while (75.00%) viewed community mitigation measures as ineffective and (66.66%) considered compensation inadequate. Additionally, (83.33%) incurred extra expenses for crop protection. Findings indicate that crop raiding significantly threatens agricultural productivity and farmer livelihoods in the region, underscoring the need for effective wildlife management strategies, improved compensation systems, and farmer-oriented mitigation approaches.

Keywords: Crop raiding, farmer perception, human-wildlife conflict, Wild boar

Introduction

Human–Wildlife Conflict (HWC) has emerged as a critical challenge for rural communities worldwide, particularly in regions where agricultural lands border wildlife habitats (Rathi *et al.*, 2020). Among the most severe forms of HWC is crop raiding, which directly impacts food security, agricultural productivity, and farmer livelihoods. Wild animals such as wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) (Chauhan, 2011), blue bull (*Boselaphus tragocamelus*) (Meena, 2017), deer, and monkeys are frequently reported as major culprits in damaging standing crops, leading to substantial economic losses (Thakur *et al.*, 2022).

In India, crop raiding is a widespread issue affecting multiple states, with millions of rupees lost annually due to wildlife damage (Senthilkumar *et al.*, 2017). Maharashtra, particularly the Vidarbha region, is highly vulnerable due to its mosaic of agricultural fields and forested areas. In Vidarbha, districts like Akola face persistent crop damage incidents, with wild boar and blue bull being the most problematic species. Farmers in Patur Tahsil are especially at risk, as many cultivate small landholdings located close to forest boundaries and water sources, conditions that attract wild animals into farmland.

Perception, in the context of human–wildlife conflict, refers to the way farmers interpret, understand, and emotionally respond to the challenges posed by wild animals (Senthilkumar *et al.*, 2017). It is shaped by personal experiences, socio-economic conditions, cultural beliefs, and the severity of losses incurred. Farmers' perceptions influence their willingness to adopt mitigation measures, report damage, and support conservation policies. A negative perception often linked to repeated losses, ineffective control methods, and inadequate compensation can lead to reduced tolerance for wildlife and increased conflict intensity (Ramu *et al.*, 2024). Understanding these perceptions is therefore crucial for developing interventions that are not only technically effective but also socially acceptable.

Although various mitigation measures and compensation schemes exist, farmers often perceive them as inadequate, delayed, or ineffective. This

results not only in financial strain but also in emotional stress and reduced tolerance towards wildlife. Understanding farmers' perceptions is essential for designing practical, community-supported solutions that align with local socio-economic realities (Senthilkumar *et al.*, 2017).

Materials and Methods

For the present study the research methodology viz. qualitative and quantitative techniques in research were accepted.

The research methodology adopted under following heads: -

1. Details of studied site
2. Sampling procedure
3. Data Analysis

1.Details of studied site

The study was carried out in Patur Tahsil of Akola District, Maharashtra, during 2024–25. The surveyed locations, as indicated on the map, are situated between 20°45' N latitude and 76°93' S longitude. The climate of Akola District ranges from tropical wet to dry, characterized by high temperatures.

Fig. 1: Map of Patur tahsil indicating villages selected for study

Table 1: Details of studied sites in Patur Tahsil of Akola district of Maharashtra.

District	Tahsil	Locations selected	Latitude	Longitude
Akola	Patur	Jirayat Patur	20°29'09" N	76°56'56" E

	Khanapur	20°27'39" N	76°56'52" E
	Malrajura	20°23'22" N	76°57'41" E
	Kothari	20°26'58" N	77°00'44" E

2. Sampling Procedure

For the present study, total of 120 respondents were selected from four different villages in Patur Tahsil, with 30 respondents chosen from each village. All respondents were selected using a simple random sampling technique. The list of eligible farmers was obtained from the Forest Department, and the final selection was made from this list. Data for the survey was collected through direct interviews with all 120 selected farmers.

The data was collected personally through face-to-face interactions. Primary data was collected through a structured interview schedule. The secondary data was collected from various books, journals, government portals, websites relevant to the investigation interest and documented systematically. Respondents were interviewed through personal interview. Prior to interview, the respondents were taken into confidence by revealing the actual purpose of the study and also full care was taken to develop good rapport with them. The interview was conducted in the most formal and friendly atmosphere without any complications.

3. Data analysis

The collected data were thoroughly examined for completeness and accuracy prior to tabulation. Appropriate statistical tools were employed, and interpretations were made accordingly. The data were processed and organized using descriptive statistics, including frequencies, means, percentages and standard deviation. Where necessary, statistical measures such as the arithmetic mean and standard deviation were applied to facilitate in-depth analysis and ensure the reliability of the findings.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Age

Table 2 presents the distribution of respondents based on their age. The respondents (n=120) were classified into three categories. In the study, (16.66%) of respondents were in the young age group, (34.17%) were in the middle-age group, and (49.17%) were in the old age group. These findings are similar with the findings of Singh (2023) and Kumar (2017).

4.2 Education

Based on the data in Table 4 the highest proportion of respondents (30.00 %) had studied up to secondary school, followed by (28.33 %) who had

completed higher secondary education. Primary education accounted for (12.50 %), while (15.00 %) were illiterate. A small proportion of respondents (8.33 %) had pursued education at the college level (Meena, 2022).

4.3 Land Holding

Table 2 shows the distribution of respondents by operational landholding. Among the 120 respondents, most were small landholders (45.83 %), followed by semi-medium (24.17 %), marginal (17.50 %), medium (11.66 %), and large (0.83 %) landholders, indicating the predominance of small and semi-medium farmers in Patur Tahsil. Similar findings have been reported by Meena (2022) and Walandkar (2007).

4.4 Annual Income

As shown in Table 2, the majority of respondents (85.84 %) had a low annual income (up to ₹200,000), followed by (13.33 %) with medium income (₹200,001–₹400,000), and only (0.83 %) with high income (above ₹400,001) (Senthil Kumar *et al.*, 2020).

4.5 Distance of farm from forest area

Table 2 shows that most respondents (81.67 %) farm very close to the forest, within 0–0.5 km. This is followed by (8.33 %) farming within 0.5–1 km, (4.17 %) within 1–2 km, and (5.00 %) within 2–3 km. Only (0.83 %) farm within 3–5 km of the forest (Vinoth, 2019).

4.6 Water body near farm

As shown in Table 2, the majority of respondents (62.50 %) reported having a well on their farm, followed by (14.17 %) with no water resource, (9.17 %) with a borewell, (5.83 %) with access to a river, and (5.83 %) with both a well and a river. A small proportion (2.50 %) reported having a canal near their farm (Maske, 2023).

4.7 Species of wild animals involved in crop raiding

The data presented in Table 2 indicates that wild boar is the most prominent species responsible for crop damage, reported by (100 %) of respondents. Blue bulls (Nilgai) were also reported by a large proportion (96.67 %), whereas deer (27.50 %) and monkeys (24.17 %) were mentioned less frequently. This finding suggest that wild boars and blue bulls are the major contributors to crop raiding in the area (Thakur *et al.*, 2022).

Table 2: Distribution of respondents according to the personal characteristics of respondents

Sr.No	Variables	Category	Respondents (n=120)	
			Frequency	Percentage
1	Age	Young (Up to 35)	20	16.66
		Middle (36 to 50)	41	34.17
		Old (Above 50)	59	49.17
2	Education	Illiterate (Uneducated)	18	15.00
		Primary (1st to 4th std)	15	12.50
		Middle School (5th to 7th std)	07	05.84
		Secondary School (8th to 10th std)	36	30.00
		Higher Secondary School (11th and 12th)	34	28.33
3	Land Holding	College (Above 12th)	10	08.33
		Marginal (Upto 1 ha)	21	17.50
		Small (1.01 - 2 ha)	55	45.83
		Semi-medium (2.01 - 4 ha)	29	24.17
		Medium (4.01-10 ha)	14	11.67
4	Annual Income	Large (Above 10 ha)	1	0.83
		Low (Up to 200000)	103	85.84
		Medium (200001 to 400000)	16	13.33
		High (Above 400001)	01	00.83

5	Distance of farm from forest area	0 – 0.5 km	98	81.67
		0.5 – 1km	10	08.33
		1 – 2 km	05	04.17
		2 – 3 km	06	05.00
		3 – 5 km	01	00.83
6	Availability of water body near farm	No any Resources	17	14.17
		Well	75	62.50
		Borewell	11	09.17
		River	07	05.83
		Canal	03	02.50
		Well + Borewell	07	05.83
7	Species of wild animals involved in crop raiding	Wild boar	120	100.00
		Blue bull	116	96.67
		Deer	33	27.50
		Monkey	29	24.17

Table 3: Perception of farmers towards crop raiding

Sr. No.	Perception	Agree	Undecided	Disagree
1	Do wild animals cause significant crop damage in your area?	80 (67.00)	38 (31.66)	02 (1.66)
2	Has crop damage led to a noticeable decrease in yield?	110 (92.00)	10 (8.33)	0 (00.00)
3	Have you or your family experienced conflicts with wild animals?	10 (8.33)	25 (20.83)	85 (70.83)
4	Are the measures developed by local communities effective in reducing crop raiding?	5 (4.16)	25 (20.83)	90 (75.00)
5	Do wildlife-related crop losses threaten farmers' livelihoods?	90 (75.00)	20 (16.66)	10 (8.33)
6	Has the loss of farm produce due to crop raiding increased the risk of food insecurity or starvation?	20 (16.66)	15 (12.50)	85 (70.83)
7	Do farmers receive adequate compensation for crop damage caused by wild animals?	00 (00.00)	40 (33.33)	80 (66.66)
8	Are traditional methods of crop protection the most effective in preventing crop damage?	5 (4.16)	30 (25.00)	85 (70.83)
9	Have modern methods of wildlife deterrence been successful in reducing crop losses?	30 (25.00)	50 (41.66)	40 (33.33)
10	Do farmers incur additional expenses to protect their crops from wild animals?	100 (83.33)	15 (12.50)	5 (4.16)

Table 3 presents the perception of farmers towards crop raiding the study revealed that crop damage by wild animals is a major concern, with (67.00 %) of farmers reporting severe damage and (92.00 %) reporting reduced yields. Only (8.33 %) experienced direct conflicts with wild animals, while (75.00 %) felt that community measures to prevent damage were ineffective. An equal proportion (75.00 %) reported income loss, though (70.83 %) believed it did not cause food shortages. Regarding compensation, (67.00 %) reported not receiving adequate payment, and none found it sufficient. Traditional mitigation methods were considered ineffective by (71.00 %) of respondents, and (42.00 %) were uncertain about the effectiveness of modern methods. Additionally, (83.33 %) incurred extra expenses for crop protection, indicating the financial strain caused by this issue.

Conclusion

From the farmers' perspective, crop raiding by wild animals is perceived as a major threat to their agriculture and livelihood. Most farmers view existing mitigation measures and compensation schemes as ineffective, and they feel the financial burden of protecting crops is increasing. While few report direct encounters with wildlife, the overall perception is that wild animal activity significantly disrupts farming and income stability.

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Fig 2: Distribution of farmers according to perception on crop raiding